

Infrastructure to Support UKRI in Green OA Compliance Monitoring

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Introduction

The UKRI OA Policy states that: “UKRI will monitor the implementation of this policy to assess compliance of research organisations and to evaluate the efficiency and effectiveness of the policy and progress towards open access.”

To meet this need for the monitoring of green OA, it is necessary to (1) continuously aggregate metadata about research papers from hundreds of repositories; (2) filter, harmonise, validate and enrich this aggregated data to raise its quality; and (3) develop compliance monitoring tools on top of it.

This section addresses the ways in which this goal can be supported by CORE (core.ac.uk), the UK national aggregator of research outputs, which has been delivered by The Open University with the support of Jisc since 2011. As depicted in Figure 1, CORE systematically aggregates metadata and full texts from repositories. CORE is also by far the most comprehensive and widely used aggregator globally. As of September 2021, CORE hosts over 200 million metadata records from over 10k repositories globally and attracts about 40 million monthly active users. Virtually all UK repositories are included and regularly harvested by CORE, making CORE strategically positioned to support its need in monitoring green OA aspects of the UKRI policy.

REF2021 compliance monitoring for RE

CORE was the official supplier of data to Research England for the REF2021 OA Audit.¹ In this capacity, CORE delivered information about OA compliance for the approximately 139k research outputs submitted to REF2021 earlier this year. Additionally, in mid-2020 CORE released a tool to support HEIs in checking compliance of their data prior to their REF2021 submission. This compliance tool, which is part of the CORE Repository Dashboard,² helps institutions to identify their non-compliant outputs, i.e. outputs deposited later than within 90 days of their acceptance.

CORE compliance monitoring comes with a powerful *cross-repository check* functionality through which it can be discovered that a seemingly non-compliant output (e.g. due to a late deposit in one repository) might be actually compliant due to a timely deposit at a repository of another institution. This demonstrates the power of aggregations in understanding where copies and different versions of the same scholarly

¹ The compliance checking method is described in detail in Herrmannova, Drahomira; Pontika, Nancy and Knoth, Petr (2019). Do Authors Deposit on Time? Tracking Open Access Policy Compliance. In: 2019 ACM/IEEE Joint Conference on Digital Libraries, 2-6 Jun 2019, Urbana-Champaign, IL, pp. 206–216. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1109/JCDL.2019.00037>

² <https://core.ac.uk/services/repository-dashboard>

publication are located across a distributed network of repositories. This is also the reason why CORE is much better positioned for compliance monitoring than individual institutions which can only rely on their limited local view.

UKRI OA policy monitoring

Similarly to compliance monitoring for Research England, CORE can deliver data required for the UKRI OA policy monitoring. The support can range from providing regular compliance reports, such as the metadata landscape report provided in earlier sections of this document, to the implementation of a dedicated UKRI dashboard. The dashboard option would allow UKRI to track the UKRI OA policy uptake in real-time, adding the functionality to slice and dice the data on-demand.

Both options could be used for answering questions including but not limited to:

- What is the proportion of research manuscripts (short vs long-form) deposited into repositories within the time period required by the UKRI policy?
- Which metadata fields in repositories are HEIs least compliant with, indicating that recommendations/guidelines/support should be put in place?
- What proportion of records is missing machine-readable licence information?
- What proportion of metadata records in repositories complies with the requirements on a variety of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), such as ORCIDs and DOIs.
- What proportion of research outputs is compliant with the UKRI policy at each institution?
- What proportion of repository records is not linked to publicly available full texts?

Additionally, the CORE aggregation can also offer a wide range of opportunities for UKRI in the area of business intelligence and supporting data-driven decision making that goes beyond the scope of the current UKRI OA policy, but are nevertheless worth mentioning in this context. In the form of one-off reports or a dashboard, CORE can be used to answering questions, such as but not limited to:

- Which research papers are associated with specific funding programmes?
- Which research topics are trending?

Fig. 1. CORE is ideally positioned to both (1) provide UKRI with the technical means for its OA policy compliance monitoring and for (2) supporting research performing organisations in meeting the UKRI OA policy requirements.

- What are the areas of research strength of specific UK HEIs?
- What collaboration networks across UK and international organisations can be identified and how do they change over time?
- What changes in OA growth can be observed after the introduction of a specific OA policy and how does this compare to other countries?

Supporting research performing organisations

CORE provides an online Repository Dashboard through which it supports HEIs in obtaining valuable information about their repository and helps them to manage its metadata and content. Repositories can freely claim a Repository Dashboard account on the CORE website.

Since its launch in 2015, repository managers and research communications professionals from more than 75 per cent of UK HEIs have registered for the CORE Repository Dashboard. Kathleen Shearer, Executive Director of COAR, states: “These services have introduced content administrators to a wealth of new information relating to their repository systems and research outputs that they were not aware of, and have made it easier for them to meet their daily tasks and speed up their efforts.”

The specific CORE Repository Dashboard functionalities which are relevant in the context of the UKRI OA policy include:

Metadata compliance monitoring: A module helping institutions to understand their level of RIOXX compliance and helping them to improve it.

Harvesting issues tracking: Provides valuable information about how a repository is seen by external systems including intelligence on harvesting errors which may need troubleshooting, thereby ensuring optimum repository health for aggregation and reporting.

Enriching metadata with PIDs: CORE regularly triangulates data across many scholarly databases to help detect

missing identifiers, such as DOIs or ORCIDs, helping repositories to import these more easily and thus raising metadata quality.

Deposit compliance monitoring: A module developed for UK HEIs helping them to monitor the time lag between publication and deposit for their outputs, as required by the REF2021 OA policy. The monitoring of this requirement is, from a technical perspective, very similar to the new UKRI OA policy requirement to deposit research articles at the time of their publication and long-form publications within a maximum of 12-months from publication and is therefore easily extensible to the UKRI OA policy.

Conclusions

CORE is singularly positioned to support UKRI with the technology it needs to effectively monitor the implementation of its policy for green OA, i.e. to assess compliance of research outputs deposited into repositories. CORE has already proven that it can be used for these purposes by validating OA compliance of the 139k REF2021 submitted research outputs for Research England. The compliance monitoring for UKRI can take two forms. CORE can either deliver reports (which can be largely automated) or build a dedicated UKRI dashboard.

Moreover, as illustrated on the example of the CORE Repository Dashboard functionalities, CORE is uniquely positioned not only to assess compliance for UKRI, but to also help institutions in becoming and staying compliant, avoiding unwelcome surprises of institutions when it is too late. By providing tools to institutions that help them become and stay compliant, the UKRI OA policy has the potential to be adopted by repositories to a larger extent, faster, with less manual labour from institutional staff and therefore also with less resistance from them.

In the future, the opportunities for UKRI in using CORE are not limited to just policy monitoring. Analysis of research trends, use of funding, research impact and collaboration patterns are all areas in which CORE can supply unique valuable data and offer expertise in digging into them.